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ABSTRACT

This document outlines the concept of RAMS characteristics for particle accelerators taking the case of the future circular lepton collider as a challenge that will be the driver for research and innovation in this domain.

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REPORT ON OPTIMAL RAMS CHARACTERISTICS FOR PARTICLE ACCELERATORS

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Executive summary

The Future Circular Electron-Positron Collider (FCC-ee) would be the largest machine ever built that will achieve unprecedented luminosities with parts-per-million energy calibration precision. Achieving substantial physics results requires for sufficiently high overall machine availability. Although the operational availability of lepton colliders has traditionally been high, the increased complexity of the new infrastructure creates a challenge to maintain these levels. The results of the analysis of the optimal RAMS characteristics revealed that the main activity of future activities should focus on the identification of the causes that have the most significant effects on downtime. This paper identifies the critical characteristics including those at system level for FCC-ee as an example for particle accelerators in general. The work is based on actual failure data of operational systems.

This report presents also a possible operation model for the FCC-ee that can be used for assessing the effect of unavailability on overall performance. Special attention is given to systems with built-in redundancies as this design concept has been proven to increase accelerator reliability.

The remainder of this document comprises the analysis of the RAMS characteristics for the FCC-ee.

1. Introduction

The Future Circular Electron-Positron Collider (FCC-ee) [1] would be the largest machine ever built by humankind. It will be 100 km long and operate in a top-up mode where new beams are continuously injected into the collider. A schematic of the accelerator complex is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: FCC-ee complex with the SPS serving as Pre-Booster. Alternatively, Pre-Booster could be a linear accelerator [1].

During its life-cycle, the FCC-ee will operate with different energies to study Z, W, and H bosons and the top quark. FCC-ee aims to increase the statistical precision of most electroweak and Higgs observable measurements by one to two orders of magnitude. Figure 2 shows the operation schedule, and Table 1

Figure 2: FCC-ee operation schedule.

shows the operational parameters and integrated luminosity goals [2] for different operation modes. The mode $t\bar{t}_1$ is an intermediate stage with 175 GeV beam energy. In Table 1 and further in this paper, $t\bar{t}$ stands for the $t\bar{t}_2$ -mode as it is the prevalent $t\bar{t}$ -mode.

Table 1: FCC-ee beam parameters in different operation modes.

Mode	Z	W	H	$t\bar{t}$
Energy [GeV]	45.6	80	120	182.5
Beam current [mA]	1390	147	29	5.4
Bunches/beam	16640	2000	328	48
Operation years	4	2	3	5
Luminosity goal [ab^{-1}]	150	10	5	1.7

Reaching the luminosity production goals requires operating the machine with 75% efficiency for 185 days per operation year [3]. This number is formed by subtracting 5% from the 80% machine availability goal to take into account the required time to refill the collider after a failure. The numbers are conservative estimates that have been based on operation experience.

Experience shows that the term availability is a highly subjective metric if it is not well defined. Following terms were initially coined in the thesis [4] to describe the availability of an accelerator:

$$\text{Machine availability} = \frac{\text{Run time} - \text{Fault time}}{\text{Run time}}, \quad (1)$$

where the run time is the scheduled operation time and the fault time is the downtime caused by failures. The likelihood of failures depends on reliability that is defined in [5] as *"probability of performing as required for the time interval (t_1, t_2) , under given conditions"*, where failure is the *"loss of ability to perform as required"*. A failure results in a fault state. The length of a fault is measured as time to the restoration that is defined as *"time interval, from the instant of failure, until restoration"*.

For an accelerator, thesis [4] also defines:

$$\text{Availability for physics} = \frac{\text{Beam delivery time}}{\text{Run time}}, \quad (2)$$

where the beam delivery time is the effective time when the beam is delivered to experiments or other accelerators, in an accelerator complex. This metric shows that an accelerator cannot always deliver a beam even though it was technically operational. The availability for physics is, however, an imprecise metric as it does not consider the rate of physics production which is measured with luminosity. In this paper, the term availability stands for machine availability to keep the text compatible with earlier paper [3].

Machine unavailability can be seen as a risk that reduces operational efficiency and in the worst-case scenario it limits a collider's ability to reach the physics goals. The European norm 31010 [6] presents a risk assessment process that consists of three steps: risk identification, analysis, and evaluation. This process is used for determining the actions that are required to treat the risk. An action can either mitigate the consequences or reduce the likelihood of a risk.

This paper presents two topics that relate to assessing the risk of unavailability in the FCC-ee. We give the first listing of critical systems for the FCC-ee and remarks on technologies that can reduce the risk. Secondly, we present an operations & availability model that can be used to analyse the system unavailability's effect on the luminosity production. The model uses the same concept [7, 8, 9] as the prior studies for the FCC-hh [10, 11]. Special attention is given to systems with built-in redundancies. They are studied first in the quantitative analysis, and their benefits are later shown in a small calculation case.

2. Lepton collider availability and accelerator availability studies

Several electron-positron colliders have been built over the years, for example, LEP at CERN; PEP-II at SLAC; KEKB at KEK; BEPC II at IHEP; and DAΦNE at INFN. Historically electron-positron colliders have had high availability. Earlier, a literature review was conducted on lepton collider availability [3], and Table 2 summarizes its findings. Additional sources of information

Table 2: FCC-ee has a conservative availability goal when compared to achieved performance in other lepton colliders [3]. However, the unprecedented size and energy compared to the other lepton colliders¹ challenges the availability records.

Machine	BEPCII	KEKB	LEP-2	PEP-II	FCC-ee
Availability [%]	89 - 94	78 - 98	86 - 92	79 - 89	Goal: 80
Circumference [km]	0.24	3.0	26.7	2.2	97.8
Beam energy ² [GeV]	1-2.3	8 & 3.5	104	9 & 3	45.6 - 182.5
Luminosity [$10^{34} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$]	0.1	2.1	0.01-0.004	1.2	200 - 1.4

^aThe presented data that was not available in [3] was taken from references [12, 13, 14, 15].

^bFor KEKB and PEP-II, the higher energy value is for an electron beam and the lower for a positron beam.

exist for availability assessment. For example, synchrotron light sources use the same technologies as electron-positron colliders. Also, the failure data from normal conducting machines at CERN and in other laboratories may be helpful.

Although, Table 2 shows that FCC-ee’s availability goal is conservative. It also shows that FCC-ee will have much more demanding operation requirements than the LEP-2, which is its closest comparison. FCC-ee will be three times larger and will operate with 75% higher energy in the $t\bar{t}$ -mode. FCC-ee will also produce luminosity at a significantly higher rate partly thanks to the far higher beam current in all but the $t\bar{t}$ -mode. These factors and the Booster ring lead to FCC-ee being a far more complex system than LEP. This is a challenge as complexity often correlates with unreliability [16] that will result in lower performance.

The low performance is not the only reason why the FCC study should be interested in availability and reliability. Increasing reliability and condition-based maintenance techniques can reduce the number of corrective maintenance interventions. This can reduce the operation costs if this allows scheduling the interventions to the “office hours” limiting the need for around the clock surveillance. Further savings can be achieved if the majority of the interventions can be performed during scheduled operation stops as this would limit the need for on-site personnel. Alternatively, if nothing is done, the number of technicians and maintenance costs will likely scale-up, and the performance will scale down compared to the LEP.

References [10, 11] provide comprehensive literature reviews on accelerator availability studies. In brief, operational availability has become more and more important as user requirements, and machine complexity has grown. OECD [17],

European Science Foundation [18] and ESFRI [19] reports on sustainable operations all mention, in various terms, that it is important to provide high-quality science services reliably and continuously.

This increased attention has produced multiple activities to assess accelerator reliability and availability. For example, in light sources, availability is one of the key performance indicators. Facilities have attempted to define common rules to calculate the availability to ensure that the results from different facilities are comparable [20]. In all cases, reliability data collection is a fundamental activity that enables other studies and allows prioritizing them. Reliability data collection has to be part of operations to achieve accurate results. The work presented in the paper [21] shows how the organization-wide reliability data collection was established at CERN. Nevertheless, this practice is still new. For example, the Capability Maturity Model Integration (CMMI) program [22] would assess the current maturity level as 1/5 “*performed process*”, as the rigor with which this task is performed varies considerably depending on the individuals managing and performing the work.

Collected reliability data is vital for modeling activities as producing relevant results depends on accurate and detailed reliability data. Modeling can be used for defining reliability requirements, estimating the effect of system reliability improvements to overall machine availability, or assessing the maintenance & operation costs. Extensive examples of modeling activities within the accelerator community include reliability studies for the MYRRHA nuclear waste transmutation facility where even a few seconds long beam trip can force a shutdown of the accelerator-driven nuclear reactor [23]. Also, the IFMIF fusion materials test facility project had an extensive reliability study that restarted the AvailSim modeling tool development [24]. The tool was initially created for ILC availability studies and has been developed further for ESS and CLIC availability studies.

Our modeling approach has relied on fault trees [25] for system failure modeling and semi-Markov models [26] for operations modeling. A Markov model consists of states and transitions between the states. At any given moment, only one state can be active. A semi-Markov model differs from a classical Markov model by the fact that the classical model only allows using exponential distributions to depict the transitions. This is not assumed in a semi-Markov model. When any distribution is allowed, the model cannot be solved analytically, and a numerical method is required to obtain a solution. We use a stochastic discrete event simulation [27] to produce the results. This kind of approach is common in complex system reliability modeling as trying to build a model that can be solved analytically results quickly in unrealistic assumptions [28].

The approach taken by the FCC study was to rely, as much as possible, on the best industrial practices, long-term experience as well as commercial services and tools. For this reason, the FCC study chose the ELMAS suite¹

¹ELMAS = Event, Logic, Modeling, Analysis, Software, see <http://www.ramantor.com/products/elmas>

as the model platform. A Finnish company called Ramentor Oy develops the ELMAS that is a Java-based, platform-independent modelling and simulation engine that implements dynamic fault trees [29]. ELMAS version 4.8 was used in our initial study [10]. It permits specifying production functions, semi-Markov chain transition logic and operation schedule specifications with user-defined Java snippets.

Our first effort to model the availability of the FCC-hh resulted in a combined availability and operations model that was validated against data from LHC operation [10]. This model is useful for risk analyses where it can be used for studying a specific risk’s impact on machine availability and luminosity production. This work, however, also recognized a need to improve the ELMAS approach. While the use of user-specified code in ELMAS gave a high degree of flexibility to tailor the tool to the domain-specific needs, it broke the concept of a single model, parameterization and simulation specification, as parts of this information were in the code. This finding motivated the development of the OpenMARS approach [7, 8]. Thesis [11] provides details on how the collider operations model was implemented initially in Ramentor’s ELMAS software and later in OpenMARS. This paper uses a further derived Analysis of Things (AoT) framework for the calculations [9].

The key performance indicator of a collider is integrated luminosity [2]. Modeling luminosity production is more complicated than modeling just machine availability. Colliders like the LHC require the machine to be filled with beam and to accelerate the beam before the luminosity production can start. The machine spends a significant amount of time preparing the beam for collisions and modeling this process is crucial to model luminosity production. Regardless of the top-up operation mode, this feature will also be necessary to model the FCC-ee operations, as frequent full refills of the machine are foreseen.

The luminosity production rate is often time-dependent. For example, in the LHC, the number of colliding particles decreases over collision time, which reduces the luminosity production rate. In our model, luminosity production is modeled with a so-called production function that can take into account time-dependency. For a collider where luminosity production rate changes as a function of collision production time, this feature is essential. In the FCC-ee, this can also be useful in certain situations. The luminosity production rate changes significantly at the start of the fill where collision production starts before the machine is entirely filled. Once the machine is filled, the luminosity production rate can be understood to be constant over a long time scale. This is not, however, the case in situations where collisions are ongoing, but the beam cannot be injected to the collider. In this paper, we assume that this situation causes the instantaneous luminosity to decay exponentially [2].

3. Qualitative availability analysis

3.1. FCC-ee Pre-booster availability

Today, two alternatives exist for implementing the Pre-booster that feeds the Booster ring: 1) the SPS at CERN or 2) a linear accelerator with 20 GeV energy.

This report studies these options based on existing availability data. In 2018, the availability of the LHC injectors was closely monitored [30], and that effort led to a credible statistics on the SPS availability. For the linear accelerator, this report uses data from SLAC's LCLS that is a hard x-ray free-electron laser with 14.7 GeV beam energy [31, 32].

In the SPS statistics [30], the SPS availability has been divided into two destinations: the LHC, and the North Area (NA) that contains fixed-target experiments. The statistics show that the LHC availability had a high priority during 2018. Due to this reason, from the two options, the SPS availability for the LHC is the more reflective indicator on what the availability could be for the FCC-ee. Overall, the SPS availability for the LHC was 92.8% and for the NA 82.8%.

In the current statistics, the downtime caused by other injectors is added to the SPS unavailability. If the SPS is the Pre-booster for the FCC-ee, its injector chain will consist of a linear accelerator, positron target, and a damping ring, as shown by Figure 1. This will be much simpler than the injector chain the SPS has had during the LHC operations. So, the majority of the SPS downtime that was caused by other injectors do not need to be considered. In total, in 2018, this was 517 hours of downtime, which is approximately 41% of the total SPS downtime. Without this downtime, the SPS availability would be 96%. However, this is not an entirely accurate number as in some instances the electrical network faults were counted as injector failures. Even though, an electrical network fault often affects the whole complex.

Regardless, the lepton beam injector for the SPS should not be ignored as a potential source of unavailability. The LEP Pre-Injector had a relatively low availability of 93-98% mainly due to issues with klystrons [33]. However, these issues could have been avoided with built-in redundancies within the accelerator systems that will be presented later in this paper.

Figure 3 shows the SPS system downtime during 2018. The provided data do not take into account the beam destination. This has several effects. Most notably, a power converter fault caused more than 200 hours of downtime for the North Area due to a decision to delay the corrective maintenance intervention. Also, the majority of the long extraction system and beam instrumentation faults only affected the North Area. The downtime linked to beam-induced failures is mainly caused by an incident where the beam loss created a hole in the beam pipe. In an injector, such a failure is mainly linked to proton operations. With leptons, the beam energy would be too low to cause damage in the SPS.

This report uses two public references to assess the availability of SLAC's LCLS. The first report [31] describes an operation period in 2008-2009 and gives about 91% availability, and the second report [32] describes a period in 2010-2011 and gives 94.8% availability. The report also defines a 95% availability goal that reserves 2% of the time for machine tuning. Based on this, reference [32] estimates that the LCLS could operate with 97% hardware availability.

All in all, both SPS and a linear accelerator can reach high availability as the Pre-Booster for the FCC-ee. As such, minor differences in the availability

Figure 3: SPS system downtime during 2018 [30]. Green bars indicate the total downtime for an individual system. Blue bars indicate the root cause duration. It disregards the downtime where the root cause of the failure is outside the system boundary. However, it includes the downtime from other systems in cases where a failure in the specific system is the root cause for other system's failures. These assumptions might not be valid for injector downtime, where electrical network faults might be counted as injector faults.

performance should not be the deciding factor between the two options.

3.2. Critical systems for availability

In all of CERN’s injectors, primary sources of unavailability have been Radio-frequency (RF) system, magnet utilities, and electricity distribution [30]. This section presents considerations on the reliability of these systems and the machine protection system that has been among top downtime contributors in the LHC.

3.2.1. Radio-frequency system

The FCC-ee and the booster will have superconducting RF-cavities. The number of cavities will change through the life cycle as the machine is upgraded to operate with different energies. Table 3 shows how the type and number of cavities change in different scenarios. Running at the Z-pole, the collider

Table 3: FCC-ee RF configuration in different operation modes [1]. The $t\bar{t}$ values are divided to values for 400 MHz and 800 MHz cavities.

Mode ¹	Z	W	H	$t\bar{t}$	
Frequency [MHz]	400	400	400	400	800
RF voltage [MV]	100	750	2000	10930	8930
Accelerating gradient [MV/m]	5.1	9.6	9.8	10	19.8
# cells/cavity	1	4	4	4	5
# cavities	52	52	136	272	372

^aValues for Z, W, and H are per beam, and for $t\bar{t}$ for both beams.

is a heavily beam loaded machine, while at the $t\bar{t}$ energy it becomes a high energy machine. This affects the design. The fast RF feedback requirements and the high number of bunches in the Z and W-modes favour design with a single cavity per power source. While in other modes a power source may feed multiple cavities and in the $t\bar{t}$ -mode the RF system could be shared with the two beams, thanks to the small number of bunches. [1]

Experience from the LEP and the LHC shows the importance of the redundant design and operational margin. In the LHC, the RF system was designed for 2 MV load, but it has been operated with 1.5 MV load, which has led to relatively high operational reliability [34]. In contrast, during the LEP operations, the RF performance was pushed beyond the design specifications [35]. During the last year of operations, the average value of the accelerating gradient reached 7.5 MV/m that is 25% over the nominal value of 6 MV/m. Even before this, in order to maximize the beam energy, the operating voltage of each individual RF unit was chosen to give the maximum acceptable trip rate so that the mean time between trips was 15 min [35]. This was sustainable as a trip would, in most cases, only affect one half-unit and LEP could survive a trip of two half units. During the last year of operations, this margin was removed, and practically all the fills ended with an RF trip.

A lesson for the FCC-ee is that a large number of cavities allows designing built-in redundancy. The LEP could operate reliably with 2/22 unit redundancy with a high accelerating gradient leading to a high cavity trip rate [35].

Assuming that the FCC-ee’s RF system will be operated with a low trip rate, the level of redundancy can be much lower than in the LEP. For example, even two units (power source and associated cavities) per beam could be a sufficient level of redundancy if the failure rates are low [34]. Still, the FCC-ee will have an additional challenge compared to the LEP as the RF systems are not shared in most of the operation modes. In this case, if an RF system loses accelerating capacity, it will only affect one beam, instead of affecting both beams symmetrically.

RF system reliability can also be enhanced with new technology. Sound operational experience with solid-state amplifiers (SSA) at SOLEIL has led many other accelerator facilities to adopt this technology to power RF-cavities [36]. In these instances, the new technology has replaced traditionally used klystrons. Experience at SOLEIL shows that SSA is a highly reliable power source. The reliability is a result of built-in redundancies that form a fault-tolerant design where the failure of a single module does not stop operations. Instead, the corrective maintenance can be scheduled to a planned operation stop. This concept is also used in CERN for PS booster [37] and SPS [38] upgrades. Reference [37] presents an analysis that shows that the redundancy in the PS booster RF powering leads to a fault-tolerant system that allows deferring most of the corrective maintenance to planned stops.

However, reliability is not the only factor that should be taken into account when deciding on powering technology. The FCC-study currently considers klystrons as the baseline powering option due to several different aspects. In Z, W, and H-modes, a single cavity requires in the order of 1 MW of power per cavity, which might limit the use of alternative technologies [39]. However, in tt-mode, the lower power requirement (200-250 kW) opens the door for different options. Another aspect are the life-cycle costs. There is an ongoing study that aims to improve the energy-efficiency of klystrons above 80% [1], which is higher than the current SSA performance of 65% [36]. On the other hand, reference [40] gives a remark that combined capital expenditure and maintenance costs could be lower for the SSA. However, this does not take into account that in the FCC the equipment will be underground. Klystrons require less space than a comparable SSA and the current plan is that the power converters for klystrons are located on the surface, which might not be the case for low voltage DC converters for SSA [39].

3.2.2. Magnet utilities

The concept of redundancy can also be applied to magnet powering. Modular power converters are used in the LHC [41] and the Diamond light source [42, 43]. They are planned for LHC experiments [44], and such structures have also been studied for the CLIC [45]. Diamond’s operational experience of fault-tolerant power converters shows the high potential of this design [46]. Diamond has 1500 power converters. During the first ten years of operations, the Diamond has had two separate years without beam trips caused by power converters. Figure 4 shows that contrary to CERN’s experience with normal conducting

Figure 4: The number of beam trips during a run caused by individual systems in the Diamond light source¹. A run consist of approximately 1000 operating hours. This Figure is based on reference [46].

machines, Diamond’s power converters are far from being the top contributor for unavailability. Due to this, adopting a fault-tolerant power converter design could significantly improve FCC-ee’s chances to reach the physics goals.

Normal conducting magnets require cooling. A survey presented in [47] shows that water leaks from the magnet cooling system are the most prominent failure mode in normal conducting magnets. This survey confirms findings from an earlier study that focused on accelerators operated by the SLAC [48]. Failure rates in the SLAC study show that the Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) of magnets are between 0.5 - 3 million hours. FCC-ee will have in the order of 10000 magnets. If the failure rate were the same as in the study [48], FCC-ee magnets would suffer a failure in every 0.5 to 2 weeks.

Most likely failure modes, in studies [47, 48], are leaks and blockage of the cooling. These failures also have relatively long recovery times. Papers [47, 48] also highlight failures due to power connection and installation failures. This list draws attention to issues such as accessibility of water cooling hoses & connections and efficient installation quality assurance testing. Magnet cooling issues will not be directly translatable to FCC-ee. Unlike many other accelerators, FCC-ee will have low field dipoles that require less cooling than high field magnets. However, lessons on cooling issues are still relevant as FCC-ee will have 10000 photon absorbers that will require water cooling [1].

3.2.3. Electricity distribution

Today, the LHC is mainly supplied by one 400 kV power source. The FCC will be supplied from three such sources as shown by Figure 5. This can impact

¹The notation X-XX designates the run number and the year (e.g., 1-15 stands for the first run of 2015). IFM stands for Installation and Facilities Management.

Figure 5: Schematic representation of the 400 kV and 230 kV lines in the Geneva region. Red dots denote the three possible 400 kV sources for the FCC [1].

reliability as the number of potential failure sources increases. However, this will also allow a redundant design, and the current plan is that FCC-ee could operate with one source missing [1]. This redundant approach is also reflected in lower hierarchy levels. Figure 6 shows the redundancy within transformer substations, alternative power sources, and the transmission line segments that connect 135/36 kV transformers. These transmission lines will allow a substation to provide electricity to an adjacent point. The high level of redundancy will alleviate issues with failures within the internal CERN network and also make operations independent from the availability of a single electricity source.

Additionally, CERN’s operations have suffered from electricity perturbations that can be caused, for example, by lightning strikes. The effect of short disturbances can be mitigated with buffers. An interesting option would be to switch from an alternating current (AC) distribution network to a direct current (DC) power distribution and to combine it with local energy buffers.

Further need for energy storing may rise from the FCC-ee Booster ring cycle. The booster injects continuously more beam into the FCC-ee. The shortest cycle length (5.6 seconds) is in $t\bar{t}$ -mode [49]. Currently, the Booster powering cycle has not been calculated. Regardless, the issue is not new and accelerator power converters have used different technologies to shield the network from the cyclical load pattern with local energy storage systems. Figure 7 presents different technologies for storing energy. Other versions of this image further mention cryogenic (liquid air) storage & hydrogen fuel cells as options with high power rating and long discharge time, and metal-air batteries as an option with low power rating and long discharge time. Shown flywheel values are for second-generation models with active magnetic bearings. Superconducting bearings (SCB) have lower electromagnetic losses and thus allow storing higher

Figure 6: Diagram of the distribution network in one grid connection point [1].

Figure 7: General characteristics of various energy storage technology options in terms of power rating and discharge time [50].

amounts of energy which allows the flywheel to provide power for a longer duration of time [51]. SCB is also more straightforward and reliable than an active magnetic bearing as thanks to the flux pinning phenomenon a SCB does not need a sophisticated control system for stable levitation.

The PS-accelerator at CERN was initially equipped with a flywheel system that was replaced with capacitors. A paper [52] published in 2005 studied dif-

ferent options on how to implement the buffer for the PS. The flywheel was rejected due to a lack of suppliers for the equipment with the required operating parameters. A direct connection to the network was rejected due to the cost of the required transformer and local reactive power compensator. The paper also identified a risk that a direct network connection might perturb operations of other CERN power converters and strengthen disturbances caused by thunderstorms. Superconducting Magnet Energy Storage (SMES) was apparently rejected due to a lack of commercial off-the-shelves industry products.

The SMES system has also been studied for J-PARC [53] and DESY [54]. The study for DESY mentions a few interesting points. The wind and solar energy are dependent on meteorological factors, and this may lead to a higher need for control reserve to ensure network stability. Also, accelerator facilities often have cryogenics production on site. This may make the SMES a more economically viable solution than in other instances where cryogenic cooling is built only to serve the SMES. The FCC-ee will have cryogenics to cool the superconducting RF-cavities and interaction region magnets [1].

For the FCC-hh, batteries are considered as a solution to store energy [55]. They will recover energy from superconducting magnets at the end of a cycle to support the powering of the accelerator during the subsequent ramp phase. Batteries appear to be a promising solution as this technology has progressed impressively over recent years, thanks to the automotive sector and the increasing use of renewable energies.

Regardless, challenges exist for batteries. Today, the capital and in some cases the operational expenditures of battery storage are higher than for most of alternative technologies. Batteries also degrade over time and usage cycles. This means that batteries have to be changed at a certain point creating more costs. Reference [56] states that for batteries, lithium-ion technology has one of the best age performances with a maximum cycle time of 20000 cycles. This is suitable for the FCC-hh that cycles a few times per day. However for the FCC-ee booster that can cycle several times per minute², this might not be suitable both due to cycle life and recharge time. Other issues include a fire hazard, which might affect a system availability, and environmental issues due to large amounts of many different metals and non-metals that batteries contain. At the start of the life cycle, the issues arise from acquiring these materials and environmental issues related to mining. Additionally, some of these materials are toxic. This creates issues in recycling batteries at the end of the life and risk of exposure to toxins through the life cycle. [56]

3.2.4. Machine protection system

Radio-frequency system, magnets, and electricity distribution are not the only sources of downtime in accelerators. The decision to dump the beam in FCC-ee will be governed by a machine protection system. The system will dump the beam if there is a high risk of uncontrolled beam losses that could

²Note, an accelerator cycle \neq a battery cycle.

damage the machine. Such a situation arises if a system required to maintain safe operation fails or if the beam becomes unstable. A key design principle in a machine protection system is to find a balance such that the system is sufficient to protect the machine but not overly complex to start to hinder the machine availability [57]. This requires a good knowledge of damage potential in failure scenarios. Uncertainty on this can lead to conservative policies that result in unnecessary dumps.

The concept of redundancy is highly present in the machine protection system. In cases where an individual sensor can trigger a beam dump, redundancy can be used to help to ensure the correct triggering. If false-positive signals are an issue, a system can be designed with a voting gate that only activates a beam dump when two out of three signals are positive. More often, a missed signal is the primary design concern. This can be tackled with an OR-gate where one out of two signals is needed to trigger a dump.

Two factors affect the availability of the FCC-ee machine protection system. Compared to the LHC, FCC-ee will be larger, and in some instances, this might result in a more complex system. Generally though, FCC-ee will be less complex as superconducting magnets will be limited to the interaction regions [1, 58] and the normal conducting magnets do not need a quench protection system, only interlocks against overheating and loss of cooling. Also, the amount of stored energy will be two orders of magnitude lower compared to the LHC [1], which will reduce the risks.

3.3. Operational aspects linked to efficiency

3.3.1. Energy calibration

Beam energy calibration by resonant depolarization is the basis for the precise measurements of the mass and width of Z and W bosons in the FCC-ee [1]. Although, lepton beams polarize spontaneously in storage rings, in the FCC-ee at the Z mode, achieving the required level of polarization could take more than 200 h [59]. This time can be shortened by using wiggler magnets that will reduce the polarization time to 45-90 min depending on the required polarization level. In the W mode, a similar time should be achievable even with spontaneous polarization.

The current plan to achieve polarization in the Z mode is that at the beginning of each fill about 200 non-colliding low-intensity bunches will be injected per beam. These bunches will be polarized for the energy measurement before the rings are filled with colliding bunches. Practically, the collider will require 45-90 min setup time before a fill.

3.3.2. Fill time

Table 1 shows that the amount of beam in the collider decreases as the collision energy increases in order to limit the amount of synchrotron radiation. This affects the fill times and the longest one is in Z-mode, where a fill lasts 17 minutes and 14 seconds [49]. In the $t\bar{t}$ -mode with the highest energy, a fill lasts 3 minutes and 44 seconds. Earlier, the 17 minutes fill time was used for

defining a 5% inefficiency budget [3] assuming that there will be about three to four failures per operation day.

The issue is more complex, as the collision production starts when the first bunches are injected [49]. This reduces fill time's impact on efficiency, as time is not entirely lost in terms of production. However, the earlier analysis did not consider the time required for energy calibration, which can be five times longer than the injection time in the Z-mode. The effects on the collider's availability for physics are calculated in section 4.1.4.

3.3.3. Injector availability

Failures occur both in colliders and injectors. In 2018, the SPS had 1063 recorded failures that lasted more than one minute. This statistic is not perfect as these failures included failures in the injector chain and were not limited to only those affecting the LHC. Failures that lasted less than one minute were not recorded systematically. A failure in an injector halts injections. FCC-ee will require continues injections to maintain a stable luminosity production level.

In the LHC, another reason for missed injections are beam quality requirements that are set to ensure machine protection and high luminosity performance. For example, in 2017, 30% of the injections were rejected [60]. For FCC-ee, this issue should not be as severe as the stored beam energy is lower than in the LHC. Also, the synchrotron radiation will have a high damping effect that may reduce the amount of beam emittance related rejections. Furthermore, some of the injection issues in the LHC are caused by the fact that beam injections occur only during fills and the beam might not be ready at the start of a fill. In FCC-ee, a new beam is injected continuously, and so these kinds of issues may only be present during a refill.

3.4. Failure recovery time

Besides the failure rates also the time required to perform corrective maintenance in the FCC has raised attention. Most concerns are linked to the longer distance between CERN sites and access points and longer tunnel sections between individual access points compared to the LHC. Regardless, there are several ways to alleviate the issue of intervention times. CERN could construct an additional site to serve points that will be far from the current sites. There are also ways to reduce the need for interventions. The build-in redundancy in design may reduce the number of failures and result in a lower number of reactive maintenance interventions. Instead, these interventions could be planned, which would lower the significance of the time it takes to access a point. Similar effect may also be achieved with condition based maintenance techniques that allow predicting the remaining useful lifetime of a system. Additionally, one could try to design accelerator systems such that the majority of critical systems would be located on the surface. This would reduce the need to enter the tunnel for repair work and shorten the intervention times.

A more technological solution on how to reduce the intervention times is to implement a robotic maintenance system. For example a futuristic vision pre-

sented in [61], describes a scenario where the Computerized maintenance management system could handle spares parts and create work orders autonomously which would be then carried out by robots. Although this scenario is far in future, the nuclear industry has used for decades remotely controlled robots to limit the radiation exposure for humans [62], and such capabilities are also developed at CERN [63, 64]. At CERN, the robots perform monitoring and emergency response tasks. Remote control requires a person to operate the robot. The field of robotics is advancing rapidly. This leads to a high uncertainty on what capabilities robots will have at the time when FCC will be operated. When assessing the feasibility of substituting human labor with service robots, it is essential to understand the intended tasks [65].

The maintenance tasks differ from the current use case of today’s assembly line robots. The tasks are non-repetitive as a robot would need to perform different kinds of interventions, and they will require some cognitive skills as it is unlikely that all the required tasks could be programmed in a robot. The question of the feasibility of automated maintenance will depend on economic factors and performance. Economic factors include the cost of the robotic system compared to human labor, the number of tasks that the robotic system can perform, and the frequency of these tasks. Performance depends on how much quicker a robot could perform maintenance compared to a human intervention. One can answer these only later in the project as the answer will depend heavily on how these technologies advance and are adopted in the industry. Basic conclusions can be already drawn like that longer distances in the FCC tunnel necessitate the use of robots and that this needs to be taken into account in design [66]. In the tunnel, space needs to be reserved for robotic systems to operate, and it is essential that systems are designed to be repaired and maintained by robots. To be able to do this in vast infrastructure like the FCC calls for industrial standards that establish norms on how the different types of equipment and the robots should be designed to be compatible with each other.

4. Availability modeling

4.1. Collider operation modeling

This section first shows what modifications are required for the FCC-hh model [11] to use it for FCC-ee operation modeling. This part is divided into operations, availability, and luminosity production to cover different aspects of the model. The developed model is then used for assessing how the unavailability affects the FCC-ee’s luminosity production performance.

4.1.1. Operation cycle model

The hadron collider model includes a distinct operation cycle model that is shown in Figure 8. It contains the following operational phases:

- Recovery: operation wait for a recovery of the collider or an injector.
- Setup: machine systems are prepared for particle beam injection.

- Injection: the machine is filled with nominal intensity bunches injected in bunch trains.
- Ramp-Squeeze & Adjust: beams are accelerated and squeezed to make a beam physically smaller and then set to collide in interaction points.
- Delivery: once adjustments are finished beams are declared stable, and experiments start to collect data from interaction points.
- Beam dump & Ramp down: beams are extracted from the machine and dumped due to an operational decision or an interlock activation in the machine protection system. After this, the energy in the magnetic fields is ramped down to a pre-injection level.

The FCC-hh cycle model needs to be altered to model FCC-ee operations. As the machine operates in a top-up mode, dedicated ramp and ramp-down phases are not needed. Also, the injector chain unavailability affects the machine operations differently. In the FCC-hh, injector unavailability affects collider operations only during the injection phase. In contrast, the FCC-ee will require new beam all the time. With continuous injections, an injector can be understood to be an on-off machine. If an injector is unavailable, the luminosity production level will decay, and a new beam can be injected normally once the injectors are available. Also, the hadron collider model simulated individual injections. This would be excessive in FCC-ee where injections occur continuously with less than one-minute frequency.

An operation cycle model can be constructed based on these assumptions. Figure 9 shows the cycle where the phase *"degraded operations"* stands for a mode where collisions are ongoing, but an injector is unavailable. The model can enter this phase either from the injection phase or from the delivery phase. Similar to the hadron collider model, a failure in the collider will trigger a beam dump, and the model will enter into the recovery phase. The model also assumes

Figure 8: Main phases of the hadron collider operation cycle [11]. The lower part of the figure shows the connection from the collider fault tree to two connections that activate if a failure occurs in the collider.

Figure 9: Main phases of the FCC-ee operation cycle with a degraded operations phase where the model enters if an injector is unavailable.

that a failure in an injector during a setup phase will cause a transition to the recovery phase.

4.1.2. Failure model

In the hadron collider model, system availability is modelled with fault trees that send information on failures and fault recoveries to the collider cycle model. The failure rates depend on the active cycle phase. This feature is important as some failures can only occur if there is a beam in the machine. The model implements this by informing the fault tree on the active cycle phase. Similarly, the fault tree informs the cycle model on failures that prohibit operations.

Built-in redundancies in different systems allow planning the corrective maintenance interventions during occasions that minimize the harm on operations. Taking this into account requires modelling an operational schedule that includes the planned maintenance interventions. Schedule modeling was done in the LHC operation model [10], but this implementation did not include deferred corrective maintenance as a feature. Implementing this is not difficult and was done to model CERN’s PSB RF system reliability as it includes built-in redundancies [37].

In this paper, just to demonstrate the functionality and to calculate basic results, only the top-level failures are modelled for the collider and injectors. The practical implementation of redundancy in system fault modeling is developed further in section 4.2.

4.1.3. Luminosity production

In the hadron collider model, luminosity production is limited to the delivery phase. This will not be the case in the FCC-ee where the collision production starts when the beam is injected into the machine [49]. Figure 10, and Figure 11 show the beam current during the injection and the delivery phases.

Availability modelling considers long time scales, and in this application, even a rough approximation of the luminosity production is sufficient. During the injection phase, the production rate is assumed to increase linearly, and in

Figure 10: Beam current in the FCC-ee during an injection phase [49].

Figure 11: Beam current in the FCC-ee during an injection phase [49]. The current imbalance between the electron and positron beams is kept within 5% with constant injections.

the delivery phase, the production rate is assumed to stay constant. With these assumptions, the instantaneous luminosity can be estimated by the equation:

$$L(t) = \begin{cases} kt + L_0 & \text{During injection} \\ L_{prod} & \text{During delivery,} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where k is the assumed slope factor for the injection phase, L_0 the instantaneous luminosity at the start of the injection phase and L_{prod} is the assumed constant production rate during delivery. Further, integrated luminosity production follows the equation:

$$L_{int}(t) = \begin{cases} kt^2/2 + L_0 * t & \text{During injection} \\ L_{prod} * t & \text{During delivery.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In the case of injector unavailability, the luminosity production rate is assumed to decay exponentially [2], and the instantaneous luminosity follows the equation:

$$L(t) = L_0 \exp(-t/\tau), \quad (5)$$

where L_0 is the instantaneous luminosity at the start of a degraded operations phase, and τ is the luminosity lifetime. Integrated luminosity is given by the equation:

$$L_{int}(t) = L_0\tau(1 - \exp(-t/\tau)). \quad (6)$$

Table 4 shows the parameter values for different operation modes.

Table 4: Parameter values for integrated luminosity calculations

Mode	Z	W	H	tt
L_{prod} [$10^{34} \text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$]	200	25	7	1.4
τ [s]	4200	3000	2520	2820
Injection time [s]	1034.8	288	150.6	224
$k = L_{prod}/\text{Injection time}$	0.222	0.097	0.056	0.007

4.1.4. Calculation

This section presents analyses on how failure and recovery rates in injectors and the collider affect the integrated luminosity production. Failures and repairs are modelled with exponential distributions that have only one parameter λ to describe failure or repair rate. A cumulative distribution function gives a probability that an event has occurred before the time x . For the exponential distribution it is given by the equation:

$$F(x) = 1 - \exp(-x/\lambda). \quad (7)$$

The exponential distribution assumes that the event probability is time-independent. For the failure rate, this is often a sensible assumption. However, for the repair rate, this assumption can cause the length of a repair to vary more than in reality. As such, using this assumption does not change the mean value, but might increase the result variance. As this analysis is mostly interested in mean values and the used assumption does not have an effect on the results.

The following calculation assumes 91% availability for collider and 91% availability for injectors. This is achieved by setting the failure rate as 10 hours and the repair rate as 1 hour, as can be seen from the equation

$$\text{Availability} = \frac{\text{MTTF}}{\text{MTTF} + \text{MTTR}}, \quad (8)$$

where MTTF is the mean time to failure and MTTR the mean time to repair. For the Z-mode, the calculation assumes a 1.5 hours long setup time for energy calibration. For other modes, the calculation assumes a 10 min long setup

Table 5: Results for integrated luminosity calculations

Mode	Z	W	H	t \bar{t}
Annual target [ab $^{-1}$]	48	6	1.7	0.34
Result [ab $^{-1}$]	47.3	6.72	1.88	0.38
Difference [%]	-1.46	10.6	12.0	11.8

time. Table 5 shows that with these assumptions the FCC-ee surpasses the annual target luminosity in all but the Z-mode. The calculation did not take into account the effect of commissioning and intensity ramp-up. For the LHC, earlier calculations have assumed that this lowers the annual performance by 10%. If this assumption was applied, the FCC-ee simulated production in W, H and t \bar{t} -modes would match the target values.

As the initial values failed to reach the target in the Z-mode, we performed a sensitivity analysis. The result in Figure 12 shows that the luminosity pro-

Figure 12: Luminosity production’s sensitivity to MTTF in the FCC-ee collider and injectors.

duction is more affected by the failure rate of the collider ring than the failure rate of the injector chain. The same effect can be seen in Figure 13, where the effects of the collider ring’s and injectors’ failure and recovery rates are studied. Collider failures affect the luminosity production more because they stop luminosity production, while a failure in an injector only reduces the production rate over time. This reduction over time is the reason why the luminosity production is more sensitive to the length of an injector failure than the failure rate. In case of a collider failure, these parameters seem equally important.

Based on the sensitivity analyses, FCC-ee reaches the target luminosity in the most challenging Z-mode when the collider MTTF is over 15 hours, and the injector MTTF is over 10 hours with 1-hour MTTR in both machines. This calculation assumes that a failure in an injector only affects the production rate. If an injector failure stopped the production, the effect would be similar to the collider failures.

Figure 13: Luminosity production’s sensitivity to MTTF and MTTR in the FCC-ee collider and injectors.

4.2. Effect of $n+1$ redundancy on system availability

4.2.1. Case description

This section demonstrates how $n+1$ redundancy in design can improve system availability. The presented case is based on the paper [67] that presents a reliability study of a power converter with built-in redundancy. The converter consists of two identical units that share the load when both of them are working. If one of them fails, the other unit will carry the full load.

This study presents how different designs of $n+1$ redundancy or the lack of redundancy affect the reliability of a system. The initial failure rates are from the paper [67] that uses Weibull distributions to depict the failure behavior. The cumulative distribution, namely the probability that a unit has failed before time x , is given by the equation:

$$F(x) = 1 - \exp(-(x/\eta)^\beta), \quad (9)$$

where η is a scale and β is a so-called shape parameter that allows modelling effects of age on the failure rate. The effect of the load is implemented with an Acceleration Factor (AF) that modifies the η parameter. The stress-relative value is gained by dividing the reference value with AF:

$$\eta_{stress} = \eta_{ref}/AF. \quad (10)$$

We will use this concept further to study how improved or reduced reliability will affect the results.

A system failure behavior is described with a fault tree that is shown in Figure 14, where a system consists of $n+1$ units and a unit has three possible failure modes. The unidentified fault stands for events where the failure cause was not recorded.

Figure 14: System fault tree, where individual units have a fault tree with three possible failure modes.

4.2.2. Calculation

Initial values for Weibull distributions' β and η parameters are presented in Table 4.2.2, where values for different current loads are calculated with the acceleration factor techniques presented in [67]. A system failure is assumed to cause 3.5 hours of downtime. The paper [67] assumes that a failure of an individual unit can be repaired on average within five days without an adverse effect on operations. Here we assume instead that unit failures are only repaired during an annual shutdown after 185 days of operations.

The calculation period duration is set as $14 * 185$ days that corresponds to the number of operational days in the life-cycle of the FCC-ee. The simulation is repeated 10000 times to gain statistically credible results. Figure 15 shows the results for systems with different $n+1$ designs and the sensitivity on the failure rate. The system in question is remarkably reliable as it is a part of the machine protection interlock system. Therefore, significant differences only appear when the reliability is decreased. Interestingly, the $5 + 1$ design is less reliable than the non-redundant design when the η parameters are reduced to 25% of the original values.

A study of different designs is somewhat abstract, especially when in the last example, different designs had different capabilities. This example examines how the redundancy affects a system that requires 20 units to function. The units are organised in clusters with different levels of redundancy. Table 7 shows the

Table 6: Weibull η and β values for different failure modes and loads². If one unit fails, and the redundancy is lost, the surviving units use the "Full load" values.

Design	1+1	2+1	3+1	4+1	5+1	Full load
Load	50%	67%	75%	80%	83%	100%
Fuse Wear η	38438	28685	25625	24024	23155	19219
Fuse Wear β	1.16	1.16	1.16	1.16	1.16	1.16
Capasitor Wear η	15350	9174	7412	6541	6086	4200
Capasitor Wear β	8.3	8.3	8.3	8.3	8.3	8.3
Unidentified η	116359	97619	91231	87766	85849	76768
Unidentified β	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9

^bThe η values are scaled to days (1 d = 24 * 60 * 60 s) like in reference [67].

Figure 15: System downtime during the FCC-ee lifetime in hours with different designs and failure rates.

considered cases.

Table 7: System design cases with different levels of redundancy.

Design	1+1	2+1	4+1	5+1	10+1	20+1	20+0
Clusters [#]	20	10	5	4	2	1	1
Total units [#]	40	30	25	24	22	21	20
Redundant units[#]	20	10	5	4	2	1	0

The highest level of redundancy 1 + 1 leads to a system that has 20 clusters with 20 redundant units and is likely to be more costly to implement. The investment should result in a more reliable system that would pay off the investment cost by providing high availability. The results in Fig 16 show that in this case, any redundancy has a positive impact on system availability, as

Figure 16: Downtime in minutes for different designs. The non-redundant design (20+0) has over 11 hours of downtime.

the downtime for 20+0 design is an order of magnitude higher compared to the 20+1 design. Regardless, the effect of the redundancy has to be always quantified as Figure 15 showed a case where the 1+0 design was better than the 5+1 design when the failure rate was high.

5. Conclusions

This paper presented a listing on availability critical systems for FCC-ee and an availability model. The listing included potential solutions to improve the reliability of power converters, RF system, and electricity distribution as these have been the lead causes of unavailability for CERN's normal conducting machines. The FCC-hh study developed an operations modelling platform that allows allocating the availability goals for different machines and studying different cases. This paper altered the existing model to represent FCC-ee operations.

The results of the simulations show that FCC-ee can reach luminosity goals with sensible failure and recovery rates. Currently, it seems that FCC-ee operations can sustain some injector unavailability despite the top-up injection scheme. The highest need for availability is in the Z-mode where the fill time and the energy calibration time are longest.

Throughout the paper, special attention was given to fault-tolerant system design as it has proven to increase the availability in many accelerator applications. This paper presented these benefits with calculation cases. Although it also showed that the benefits need to be quantified. Adapting the fault-tolerant design in various FCC-ee systems will help to ensure that the collider reaches the luminosity goals.

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